

**Regional Mithraism: A Preliminary Study of Localised Cult Practice
in the Western Roman Empire**

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Introduction

The ancient world was undoubtedly varied. One might envision it as a 'melting pot'; the contents of which contained a plethora of different ideas, perspectives and experiences of a truly diverse breadth of people. The Roman world was no different and neither was its empire a static entity. Its borders were not ephemeral, but penetrable. Its fundamental nature was thus permeable, and it could therefore transform itself in accordance with the lived experiences of the people it sought to assimilate. One such experience, still very much pertinent today, is that of religion. Religion in the Roman world was complex and mixed. Before the state adoption of Christianity in the 4th century CE, the vast majority of Roman people trusted in the traditional Graeco-Roman pantheon. This polytheistic hierarchy was very much cemented in Roman society and its people focused on a predominantly contractual relationship with the divine, rather than to the adherence of complete religious dogma (King C, 2003, pp. 301-3). One consequence of this manifested in the form of pragmatic ritual behaviour and strict expressions of religious knowledge. Despite this, one mustn't assume that Roman religion was therefore unsusceptible to outside influence. Nowhere better is this evident than in the exotic 'mystery cults' of the eastern Empire.

These cults provided a 'religious package' to a wide number of Roman people, promising to answer both the cosmogenic and eschatological questions of human existence (Drummond, 2013). The tradition of promising '*gnosis*' or 'secret knowledge' shares its origins with places all over the Roman empire, though more commonly with the east, in Egypt, Greece, Anatolia and Persia (Henig, 1984, p. 95). The emergence of these cults can be attested to the 1st century CE, though it is not until the following century that we see tangible evidence for their widespread practice (ibid). The evidence for their existence is profound and visible in a variety of different milieus of Roman society. The religious ideologies present across these regions were no doubt distinct and in some cases, greatly different to the established religious customs in the Roman Empire before the turn of the 2nd century.

The cult of Mithras is a particularly fascinating mystery religion which concerned the worship of an Indo-Aryan deity from pre-Roman Persia. The cult's rich iconography

often depicts Mithras in Persian dress and his name appears to be closely associated with *Avesta*, the Persian deity of light (Henig, 1984, p. 83). Epigraphic evidence would suggest that the cult was male exclusive and particularly popular among soldiers of various ranks (Gordon, 1980), though he is known to have been worshipped by merchants and a number of Roman elites (Walsh, 2018, p. 20). Little is known about the rituals that were integral to the cult, however, it widely accepted that its followers constructed their temples or *mithraea* partly underground so as to emulate a central narrative of Mithras and his creation of the universe (Clauss, 2000, pp. 43-4). This narrative is frequently depicted in mithraic iconography and shows Mithras killing the cosmic bull *Taurus* within a cave; a scene otherwise known as the *Tauroctony* (Fig 1).

Figure 1 Marble relief of the 'Tauroctony' - British Museum, Inv. No 1825,0613.1

The evidence for the cult is useful in conceptualising the assimilative nature of Roman paganism and it has left a remarkably distinct signature on the archaeological record.

Interpretations surrounding the cult, its religious function and organization have only been manifested as a result of the unique evidence which appears in excavations throughout Europe and the Middle East. This abundance of material is part of the reason as to why Mithraism is fast becoming one of the most versatile fields of study within Roman archaeology. With that said, there is an increasingly worrying development in Mithraic studies, one which concerns the homogenous nature of this evidence.

Current frameworks for understanding the cult of Mithras are very much aligned with the idea that this distinct archaeological signature is indicative of a shared religious system, one that was not just recognizable across the Roman empire but was completely understood in all environments (Dirven & McCarty, 2014). Many are inclined to continue interpreting the cult as a universally standardised organization, as if its features, rituals and knowledge were all the same throughout time and space. However, the cult of Mithras has never strictly presented evidence for such a framework and the recognizable characteristics of it across the Roman empire are not representative of the vast number of idiosyncrasies that persist within its 'archaeological signature' (ibid).

Aims and Objectives

This dissertation sets out to do exactly this. It aims to present the study of Mithraism as it currently exists within discourse in order to illustrate its contextual flaws and inconsistencies. In explaining where Mithraic scholarship currently stands, it is hoped that we may begin to consider the academic potential in rethinking our modes of understanding. In order to do this effectively, this work has put together a provincial account of Mithraic evidence which shows deviation in the cult to varying degrees. Of course, it is first necessary to present and examine the homogenous characteristics of the cult so that we are better able to conceptualise the extent of localisation. With that said, it is important to realise that this work does not set out to refute the presence of homogeneity within Mithraism, rather it aims to bring to the forefront the academic potential of understanding the development of worship to Mithras, in its regional contexts. It supports the move towards a more localised analysis of Mithraic evidence in future discourse so that our understanding of it is better placed within the fast-increasing study of Roman religion.

The evidence presented in this dissertation is derived from the Roman provinces of Italy, Gaul and Britain. This work will aim to discuss the wider factors for the development of variation with the cult of Mithras in each of these provinces. With that said, this is simply a preliminary study and the vast breadth of evidence we have for the cult cannot be analysed entirely within the word constraints of this essay. However, it is hoped that the discussion will elucidate the generic problems within this homogenous understanding of religious practice, rather than interpret the complex nature of localised variation.

Literature Review

The Dawn of Mithraic Studies

Before discussing how the study of Mithraism has developed, it is worth understanding how it first came to be. The earliest pioneer of Mithraic studies was Franz Cumont, a Belgian archaeologist who had published a series of books on the nature of Roman paganism. Cumont's first main publication was a two-volume classification of Mithraic archaeology titled '*Textes et monuments figurés relatifs aux mystères de Mithra*', (1894-1900). It focussed exclusively on the archaeological evidence for the cult in the Roman Empire and was later translated and republished under the single title: '*The Mysteries of Mithra*' (1903). Cumont's interpretations of Mithraic evidence were cemented in the notion that the cult came from the Persian state religion of Mazdeism, though further suggesting that it maintained its past traditions with minor divergence from its original context (Cumont, 1903, p. 104). He also published an extensive map on the dissemination of the cult (Fig 2) and later more general books on Roman paganism (Cumont, 1911, 1922). In fact, he was one of the first to suggest there existed a religious rivalry between Christianity and Mithraism, in which should the latter have succeeded in being widely embraced, the west would have maintained an 'Eastern style' theocracy (Praet, 2014, pp. 291-2). This, he suggested would have had major implications on the social and scientific development of Western civilization (ibid).

Today, Cumontian approaches are less favourable in academic discourse. Many of his views are simply refuted (Ulansey, 1991, p. 10), though not always for lack of evidence. Instead, Cumont exemplified the social, political and thus scholarly norms of European imperialism and as such many of his notions projected these norms onto the past. When coupled with religion, the result was essentially a pagan versus Christian dichotomy, in which the latter represented the virtuous and civilising embodiment of the western world (ibid). Of course, Cumont was not the only scholar to do so. His views were often mirrored in the works of archaeologists such as Francis Haverfield (1906) and R.G. Collingwood (1923) and it wasn't until the development of post-colonial critiques in the 1970s, that issues pertaining to such views were brought to light as deeply impactful within a number of modern disciplines (Hingley, 2014). Roger Beck, another expert of Mithraism, has proved useful in contextualising the

development of Mithraic studies since Cumont (1984). However, it would seem that no solid discussion has taken place since and so it might be a matter of interest among scholars to review where the study currently stands.

Figure 2 Cumont (1903, p. 29)

The Origins of Mithras

Cumont was fond of the idea that the cult of Mithras was closely associated with the religious practices of pre-Roman Persia and therefore it represented a 'Romanised' form of ancient Zoroastrianism (Beck, 1987, p. 298). He suggested that Mithras arrived in the Roman world fully accompanied by other Persian deities and that the cult must therefore have remained largely the same as it was before (Cumont, 1903, pp. 104-

7). However, in the advent of increased speculation and the emergence of post-colonial critiques, Cumont's view received an unprecedented amount of criticism. In the early 1970s, John Hinnells considered this narrative to be conflicting with the vast amounts of Mithraic iconography across the Roman empire, particularly with respect to the *tauroctony* scene (Fig 1) (Hinnells, 1975). Since then, reassessment of the evidence has allowed for other theories to emerge and many support that the cult was a product of the city of Rome (Beck R, 2002). The evident associations of Mithras with ancient Persia would suggest that followers of the cult understood him to be a Persian deity, and he was worshipped as such within the context of Roman society (Luther, 2004)

Universal Mithraism

In keeping with the main interest of this study, it must be considered, that the approaches discussed only function on the basis that the cult's features, ideologies and religious practices were universally consistent throughout the Roman empire. The vast majority of scholars, therefore, were working under the assumption that there existed a 'Mithraic canon', one that must have been fundamentally recognizable throughout the Roman world. One scholar who set the scene for such a framework to endure was Reinhold Merkelbach. Merkelbach's *'Mithras'* (1984) provided ample coverage of Mithraic iconography, epigraphy and architecture from around the empire. It contains thousands of pictures of Mithraic archaeology, all of which are presented in an accessible typological format; the likes of which had not been seen since Maarten Vermaseren's two volume *'Corpus Inscriptionum et Monumentorum Religionis Mithricae'* (1956 and 1960). An unavoidable result of this format, however, was a lasting presentation of Mithraism as religion of inherent homogenous characteristics. Some scholars have done little to reassess the problems presented by Merkelbach, though Richard Gordon recently stated that his publication presents the cult of Mithras as a 'platinizing theology' (2014, p. 757).

Others, such as Roger Beck, have formed the vast majority of their interpretations without considering the evidence of variability in detail. In his 2006 publication *'The Religion of the Mithras Cult in the Roman Empire: Mysteries of the Unconquered Sun'*, Beck dedicates an entire chapter to the layout of mithraea (Fig 3), suggesting that they

follow a 'blueprint' which was architecturally representative of the cult's cosmogenic beliefs (pp. 103-112). He does acknowledge that not all mithraea follow this layout (p.103), however, he undoubtedly supports that all are constructed with the intention of representing a Mithraic model of the world, one that was closely related to the zodiac (Fig 4). Such an interpretation is intrinsically dismissive of varied religious knowledge and supports a classic model in which the beliefs among ancient mithraists were both universal and recognizably projected onto their world. His framework, though perhaps viable where underlying homogeneity exists, cannot be considered wholly applicable to mithraea in all circumstances due to the mere existence of regional variation.

Figure 3 *Basic plan of a mithraeum*
(Walsh, 2018, p. 142)

Figure 4 Beck's 'Blueprint of a mithraeum', showing a complex model of mithraic astrology. The scene represents the interior of a mithraic sanctuary, with typical raised podia on either side of the central nave, and The 'tauroctony' relief as the main figure. (Beck, 2006, p. 103).

Where is the Study Now?

Since the turn of the 21st century, many interpretations concerning the nature of Mithraism have been primarily subject to post-processual frameworks. Many hark back to the work of Richard Gordon with his *'Mithraism and Roman Society: Social Factors in the Explanation of Religious Change in the Roman Empire'* (1977) which no doubt set the precedent for the emergence of social analyses of the cult. In fact, Gordon could possibly be considered the first to acknowledge the significance of variation within Mithraism:

'Yet, this kind of generalization will not help explain peculiarities of the distribution of each of these cults; nor will it help us to understand their role as 'established sects', to use a modern analogy' (p. 94)

Though he does not discuss variation in detail, he clearly acknowledged that by generalising various aspects of the cult, we are not gaining a clearer picture of its function in Roman society. Others such as Lucinda Dirven and Matthew McCarty have recently been credited with a truly fascinating discussion on artwork within the cult of Mithras (Dirven & McCarty, 2014). Their work supports that the thousands of reliefs across the empire evidently support some form of 'Mithraic schema', however more attention needs be given to differences and variations among them. In doing so, we may begin to interpret the 'social life' and agency of Mithraic iconography, which was inevitably tangled up with concepts of identity. Matthew McCarty has also recently published an article on how variation in depositional rituals, might shed light on how religious knowledge in Mithraism was not only demonstrated but transmitted across different communities (McCarty, 2019). This is something which had been conceptualised by Richard Gordon two decades before, with his insightful suggestion of travelling Mithraic 'colporteurs' (Gordon, 1994). Eric Rebillard and Jörg Rüpke, have also provided useful models of social and individual identity among religious communities of the ancient world (2015). Though not specialists in Mithraic studies, both Rebillard and Rüpke have presented modes of understanding which support a move towards a more regional and localised analysis of ancient religion, in which the individual, rather than the tradition itself, ought to be the focus of the modern day scholar (p. 11).

Despite this, professionals in the field of Mithraic archaeology are sometimes reluctant to provide an account of regional variation and discuss its implications on our modern interpretations of the cult. Though there is an evident upwards trend towards the study of variation, there has yet to be a comparative and contextual presentation of this evidence in scholarship. It is hoped, therefore, that this study can act as a preliminary filler of this evidential gap and utilise some of the concepts put forward to further illustrate its academic potential in current and future frameworks. It will avoid

discussions of the cult's origins for risk of falling into further debacle as is often the case in post-Cumontian interpretations. This is also the case with regards to various cosmological approaches, like those presented by Roger Beck. However, it will endeavour to acknowledge the importance of cosmology and ancient astronomy as central to the religious knowledge of Mithraism in a number of different sites across the Western Empire.

Methods of Study

Though unable to attain any primary data, this study has largely utilised the works of Vermaseren's '*Corpus Inscriptionum et Monumentorum Religionis Mithraicae*' (1956 and 1960) (CIMRM) to bring together a holistic presentation of a wide range of Mithraic material from the western Roman provinces. The CIMRM is still the most referenced index of Mithraic archaeology in scholarship, however, the vast majority of new evidence uncovered since, has not been added to it. The original volumes of the CIMRM are difficult to obtain and in light of this, Roger Pearse has set up a website dedicated entirely to collection of old and new Mithraic material, including most of the CIMRM (Pearse, 1999). This has proved extremely useful in the formation of this dissertation and thus the abbreviation 'CIMRM' will be used in citing both Vermaseren's Corpus and the material presented by Pearse.

With regards to the format of evidence in this study, material is presented in accordance with its associated province so as to support the underlying focus of this work: localisation. Generally speaking, there are three primary forms of evidence that can be considered characteristic of Mithraism. The first and most common is purely iconographic, where Mithras is depicted in a number of different scenes with his companions, either in sculpture or relief. The second would be the presence of the *mithraeum*, the underground sanctuaries in which followers of the cult would have worshipped, undertaken initiations and performed important rituals. The third is evidence for ritual activity.

Nonetheless, before even considering presenting the evidence for variation within the cult of Mithras, it is first necessary to showcase its features that are considered inherently homogenous. The evidence collected for this study is therefore presented in two parts. The first will showcase aspects of the cult that one might consider common and universal. Without understanding what makes the cult homogenous in the first place, it would be practically impossible to locate and present evidence that is varied or diverse. The second part showcases the evidence which undoubtedly conforms to such common practices but is instead inherently idiosyncratic in either minor or major ways.

The Archaeological Evidence

Part I

Common Themes and Features

Iconography

The 'Birth of Mithras'

Due to the lack of ancient literature for the cult of Mithras, it has always been necessary for scholars to analyse its iconographic evidence in order to reconstruct its most central narratives. With that said, there are a few limited sources that we can turn to which tell us about the nature of such stories, particularly concerning the deity's birth. Justin the Martyr, a 1st century Christian apologist declared that the god was 'born of a rock'¹ and another unidentified writer from the 2nd century conceptualises a story in which Mithras 'spills his seed onto a rock' (Clauss, 2000, p. 62). Similar depictions have been made in the writings of Commodian² and then later John the Lydian in his account of different pagan festivals³ (Vermaseren, 1951, p. 286). Though a number of these authors were fairly contemporary with the advent of Mithraism, all write from a Christian perspective and are therefore often condemning of the cult. However, when coupled with iconographic evidence, the literature holds true, and it is generally accepted that many Mithraists envisioned the birth of their deity to have been associated with a rock.

A scene often depicted in relief shows Mithras either protruding from said rock, or emerging from one, bearing a torch in one hand and a blade in the other (Fig 5). Others are naturally more complex with depictions of other deities and sometimes zodiacal animals (Fig 6). Others were carved into rock itself and clearly served a more visual function (Clauss, 2000, p. 63). In any case, the belief that Mithras was 'born of a rock' was essential to the fundamental cosmic narrative of the cult and its abundance attests to a fairly wide-spread acceptance of this story.

¹ Justinus, *Dialogue with Trypho*: 70

² Commodian, *Instructions* 1, 13

³ John the Lydian, *De Mensibus* 4, 30

Figure 5 The 'Birth of Mithras' as depicted on a marble relief from Rome, (CIMRM 353)

Figure 6 Damaged marble statue of the 'rock birth' from Romania. Mithras is emerging from his upper body, whilst a snake is wrapped around it (CIMRM 1991).

The Tauroctony

The scene of Mithras killing the cosmic bull is the most common illustration we have from the cult and it is easily the most recognizable (Fig 7). In the scene, Mithras is depicted straddling the bull with a blade to the animal's throat. In almost all examples he is surrounded by the torchbearers Cautes and Cautopates, alongside a snake, scorpion and a dog. Each of the animals are illustrated in some antagonistic action towards the bull. The dog and snake are usually seen licking the blood of the animal and the scorpion lies between its legs. Mithras is commonly depicted wearing traditional Persian dress, including a Phrygian cap and a knee-length tunic with an extended cape.

Figure 7 Marble tauroctony 2nd century CE, Rome (CIMRM 606) Royal Ontario Museum In No: 927.68

In less visually simplistic illustrations, tauroctony reliefs might be surrounded by subsidiary panels, depicting various zodiacal figures or scenes relevant to the cosmic narrative of Mithras (Fig 8). In the example from Sterzing, the relief has been reconstructed with extensive colour. The act takes place within a cave and Sol and Luna, other solar deities, are pictured as key components of the design. This particular example, however, is not entirely representative of what we would expect to find in all Mithraic contexts.

Figure 8 Tauroctony' scene - a modern reconstruction of CIMRM 1400, from Sterzing, Austria

The Mithraeum

Layout and Architecture

The buildings in which followers of the cult of Mithras met and engaged in religious activity were known as *mithraea* (singular: *mithraeum*). Remains of various mithraea appear across the provinces of the western Roman empire and as stated earlier, they exhibit a remarkably distinct archaeological signature. In most instances, these structures adhered to a very simple layout, consisting of a central nave, two opposing benches and a niche in which the tauroctony was placed (Figs 3 and 9). Some also had a *narthex* or 'ante-chamber' at the entrance of the building, which may well have been used to store various foodstuffs (Claus, 2000, p. 45).

Figure 9 Plan of the mithraeum at Martigny, Switzerland. C: Nave, d: Benches, e: apse, A: narthex.

<https://www.mithraeum.eu/monument/65>

Most interesting, however, is that the vast majority of them were constructed below ground level; the intention behind which was probably to emulate the setting a cave (ibid pp. 43-4). This undoubtedly harks back to the sacred narrative of Mithras and the

Bull. In fact, both literary and epigraphic evidence indicates that originally many followers used words such as *spelaeum* (cave) and *crypta* (underground corridor) to refer to these sanctuaries (Bjørnebye, 2007, p. 13) and therefore, constructing them in a manner that was representative of a cave can be considered to have been an intrinsic part of cult practice. In some cases, there is evidence to suggest that the interior of a number of mithraea were also decorated with basalt to further roughen the walls and ceilings of the sanctuary, so as to further emulate the physical characteristics of a cave setting (Walsh, 2018, p. 7).

Astrological Symbolism

In returning to Roger Beck's notion that mithraea aimed to exhibit a cosmological 'blueprint', there are some which do indeed have iconographic representations of the zodiac and other celestial beings, though Beck suggested that the only known mithraeum to have fully lived up to this 'blueprint' was Sette Sfere (Seven Spheres) in Ostia (Fig 10), as its interior was decorated with mosaics depicting various solar deities (Beck R, 2006, pp. 151-2). He also suggested that the exterior of mithraea lacked decoration as more focus was emphasised on the symbolic nature of the mithraeum's interior (ibid p. 106).

Figure 10 Mithraeum of the 'Seven Spheres' Ostia, CIMRM 239

Ritual Evidence

Initiation

In terms of the rituals that took place within these mithraea, very little has presented itself as solid evidence. Most of what we think we know derives from more Christian writers, who emphasised intense initiations ceremonies above all other forms of ritual activity (Clauss, 2000, p. 102). For example, the pseudonymous 6th century writer Nonnus paints a picture in which cult initiation included over eighty different rites. Some of which were clearly physically demanding:

“They who are going to be received into the Mithraic cult, are initiated by undergoing a series of trials... for example, they first all leave the initiate to fast for fifty days... they are ‘chafed’ for two days and left in the snow for twenty days.”⁴

Naturally, there exists no further evidence in support of the claims made by Nonnus as the very nature of such activity is very unlikely to have left a distinct archaeological signature. With that said, if we return to the widely accepted idea that the cult was favoured among military men (Campbell, 2013), then it is viable to suggest that such activities did take place as it may have been attractive for those who were already hardened to the physical demands of the Roman army (De la Bédoyère, 2002, pp. 174-182).

At the mithraeum of Santa Maria Capua Vetere, there is a series of painted panels which could be potentially illustrating an initiation ceremony (CIMRM 187-193). Though some of the panels are not so clear, the first depicts three males (Fig 11). One is dressed in a short white tunic and guides another who seems to be blindfolded. This is quite significant as the act of being blindfolded is something which the writer Ambrosiaster confirms:

‘They are deceived in the cave, where they have their eyes blindfolded’⁵

⁴ Migne, PG 36: 989

⁵ Ambrosiaster, *Quaestiones vesteris et novi testament* 113.11

Another panel shows a mystagogue in a Phrygian cap with an outstretched sword to the initiate, who is kneeling with his hands bound (Fig 12). The third shows the initiate with a crown on his head (Fig 13) something which is again present in the words of Tertullian (*De Cor.* 15. pp. 134-5).

Figure 11 Panel 1 (CIMRM 187)

Figure 13 Panel 3 (CIMRM 189)

Figure 12 Panel 2 (CIMRM 188)

The Ritual Feast

There is also a considerable amount of iconographic evidence which depicts Mithras engaged in a feast with his companions (Fig 14). Beck considers it to have been the most common depiction of Mithras after the tauroctony (Beck R, 2004, pp. 286-7) and one would assume that the presence of raised benches in the mithraeum itself supports a perfect setting in which mithraists could banquet. Tertullian also maintained that feasting was an important aspect to Mithraic ritual as, similar to the Christian eucharist, it emphasised the concept of eternal life by resembling resurrection (Clauss, 2000, pp. 108-9).

Figure 14 Reconstruction of CIMRM 1896. Two-sided relief showing Mithras and companions in ritual banquet. Konjic, Bosnia.

Moreover, the number of animal bones recovered from excavations of mithraea clearly indicate that preparation of food took place. This is especially prevalent in Gaul and Britain with preference towards ox, sheep and chicken (King, 2005, pp. 353-355). It is not known if such animals were sacrificed before preparation, however, some mithraea seem to have been scattered with various bones or appear intentionally deposited at the later phases of use (Richmond & Gillam, 1951, p. 40).

Ritual Deposition

This intentional deposition is not limited to animal remains. In fact, a number of sites produce evidence for scattering or deposition of various objects, reliefs and even coins. Before the beginning of the 4th century, a common votive practice was deposition of cult imagery, altars and epigraphy as is evident particularly on the Danubian and Rhine frontiers (Walsh, 2008 p. 38). Many of these objects were broken apart and buried, some of which had representations of Mithraic narratives on them, as is the case from this ceramic vessel from Bornheim-Sechtem (Fig 15). However, towards the end of the century, we begin to see a more widespread practice of coin deposition, especially across Gaul, at sites such as Martigny, Trier and Les Bolards (Walsh, 2018 p. 33).

Figure 15 Ceramic fragments of a vessel from Bornheim-Sechtem (Ulbert, Wulfmeier, & Huld-Zetsche, 2004 fig 6)

Some Mithraic communities constructed small wooden or ceramic boxes containing animal bones, coins and fragmented pottery (Fig 16). It would seem that many were intentionally buried near mithraea during the earliest phases of activity, something Matthew McCarty suggests represents a foundation ceremony which was symbolically relevant to the opening of a mithraeum (McCarty, 2019). David Walsh has written extensively about the nature of the decline of Mithraism (Walsh, 2018). He puts forward the notion that the intentional fragmentation and deposition of items might also be symbolically representative of religious closure (p. 55). That, as well as there having existed early foundation deposits, later occurring fragmentation must allude to some kind of closing ritual (ibid).

Figure 16 tile foundation deposit box containing charred animal bones and carbonised seeds. *Apulum Mithraeum III* (McCarty, 2019, p. 287)

Archaeological Evidence

Part II

Variation and Idiosyncrasies

Rome and Italy

Iconography

If we are to accept the current interpretations regarding the origins of the cult, then one would assume that Italy was home to the earliest depictions of Mithras. Generally speaking, this holds true and the earliest known tauroctony scene is attested to the city of Rome (FIG 17). It dates to the beginning of the 2nd century CE and was likely dedicated by a slave of one of the city's praetorian prefects, Tiberius Claudius Livianus (Clauss, 2000, p. 22). The key components to this scene are no different than what we would expect to see and a possible reason for this might be due to its early origins.

Figure 17 Very early tauroctony sculpture from Rome. Inscription reads:

'ALCIMUS T. CL(AUDI) LIVIANI SER(VUS) VILLIC(US) S(OLI) M(ITHRAE) V(OTUM) S(OLVIT) D(ONUM) D(EDIT)' (CIMRM 593-4)

Despite this, there is an evident trend emerging from the mid 2nd century, in which a number of Mithraic communities in Italy decided to paint their tauroctony scenes in elaborate frescos, rather than have them commissioned in sculpted relief. In Rome, for example, the Barberini mithraeum (CIMRM 389) has a remarkably well preserved painting of the sacred narrative (Fig 18). It is a fairly complex scene surrounded by further story panels, similar to sculpted relief from Sterzing (Fig 8). Mithras is dressed in a blue tunic, his cloak red with seven stars painted on its interior side. The dog, serpent and scorpion are all present, including the torchbearers. The 12 zodiacal animals are depicted across the top of the fresco alongside what Vermaseren considered to be illustrations of the traditional Graeco-Roman deities Jupiter and Oceanus-Saturnus (CIMRM 390). Another painted fresco is known from a mithraeum near the Baths of Titus, though it assumed to be lost (CIMRM 337).

Other painted iconography is present in Rome, such as at the Santa Prisca mithraeum, though in this instance the tauroctony is sculpted and the painted illustrations are stand-alone depictions of a Mithraic procession (CIMRM 480) and another of Sol (CIMRM 483). Though clearly present in Rome, it would seem that the decision to use paint to depict Mithraic iconography is even more prevalent elsewhere in Italy. As discussed in Part I, the mithraeum of Santa Maria Capua Vetere used paint to depict initiation scenes (Figs 11-13). The tauroctony scene at Capua Vetere was also highly elaborate and painted as a fresco on the western wall of the central nave (Fig 19).

Figure 18 Painted fresco of the tauroctony, Barberini mithraeum, Rome (CIMRM 390)

Figure 19 Tauroctony fresco, Capua Vetere (CIMRM 181)

In this example, all the main components and characters are present, though note that the bull is white, rather than its usual brown. Mithras is wearing a predominantly red tunic with green seams and his shoes and sheath are both yellow. His Phrygian cap is red, alongside the exterior of his cape; the interior of which is again illustrated with seven stars. In the top left corner is Sol looking down at Mithras and a field is visible in the foreground. In another separate painting near the central podium of the room, Cautes is depicted between two laurel trees, next to a rooster and burning altar (CIMRM 182). Another shows Luna within an arch shaped frame, she seems to be driving a horse-drawn carriage with a whip in her hand (CIMRM 184). The only other painted fresco in Ostia comes from the 'Mitreo delle Pareti Dipinti' which has three separate panels depicting a woman in a field. Vermaseren suggested that there was probably another painted tauroctony in the sanctuary as there are traces of blue, red and brown on its centre wall (CIMRM 268).

A number of mithraea in Ostia also used mosaics to depict other relevant figures and scenes. We already discussed the mosaic flooring at the Seven Spheres mithraeum (Fig 10), which Beck believes was the most highly elaborate in all of Italy (Beck, 2006, pp. 151-2). Seven Spheres also had mosaic depictions of the torchbearers within the benches themselves, which is not seen anywhere else in the Empire (Figs 20-1). Elsewhere in Ostia was the mithraeum of the 'Planta Pedis' which is characterised by an entirely mosaiced floor, in which are simple depictions of a serpent and a footprint (CIMRM 272).

Another increasingly noticeable element to the Mithraic iconography in Italy is the inclusion of other Graeco-Roman deities. For example, alongside the mosaics at the Seven Spheres mithraeum were depictions of Jupiter, Saturnus, Venus, Mars, Mercurius and Diana-Luna (CIMRM 241). Similarly, at Capua Vetere a marble relief was uncovered from a recess in the Mithraeums' southern wall. It depicts the Greek deities Eros/Amor and Psyche (Fig 22). This particular relief is the only known example of the pair and they are not traditionally associated with the cult of Mithras at all within the Roman empire (Luther M, 2015 p. 107)

Figures 20 and 21 Mosaic depictions of Cautes (left) and Cautopates (right) (CIMRM 243)

Figure 22 Marble relief showing the child Eros/Amor grabbing the arm of a winged Psyche (CIMRM 186)

Mithraea

One particularly interesting aspect to mithraea in Italy, is that a large number of them are not stand-alone structures at all. Almost all were constructed as part of pre-existing buildings or built within others that served wholly different purposes in the past. This is glanced at by Clauss who gives a brief overview of the nature of temple structures in Rome and Ostia (Clauss, 2000 pp. 43-4). He tells us that mithraea in both of these cities formed part of private buildings, to which only well-off people could attend (ibid). David Walsh's account is much more informative. As well as providing images and plans of Italian mithraea, he discusses the general pattern to which many in Italy followed, acknowledging that the spatial variation of them in Rome is indicative of the potential for variation to occur elsewhere in the empire (Walsh, 2018 p. 20).

One of the most prolific examples of a mithraeum forming part of a public building, is the Crypta Balbi. It does not appear in Vermaseren's CIMRM due to the fact that it was discovered in 2000 and unfortunately the excavation reports have not been translated (De Grossi Mazzorin, 2004). The Crypta Balbi forms part of the theatre and porticus of L. Cornelius Balbus and was constructed near the turn of the 3rd century CE (ibid) (Figs 23-4).

Another Mithraeum was found connected to the Circus Maximus. It dated to the middle of the 2nd century CE and lies four storeys under the city's modern foundations (CIMRM 434). Its layout is not as conventional as expected as it seems to have incorporated five separate adjacent rooms (ibid). Similar mithraea connected to public buildings are present in Ostia. One in particular was constructed underneath the foundations of Hadronic period bathhouse and was only accessible down a long flight of steps (CIMRM 229). The structure is long and narrow with a vaulted ceiling and the marbled tauroctony was found in situ, above which was an opening in the ceiling that acted as a skylight (ibid).

Figures 23 and 24

Lef: Reconstruction of the Crypta Balbi mithraeum. Below: Plan

What seems to be more common, however, are mithraea that are connected to private buildings such as *insulae* apartments and elite houses. On the Esquiline hill in Rome, a mithraeum was uncovered, hidden at the back of a 2nd century *Domus* (CIMRM 246-60). Otherwise known as the Via Santa Giovanni Lanza mithraeum, it remains one of the smallest and most composite ever uncovered in the empire. The entrance into the structure was found next to an aedicule which housed *in-situ* statues of various deities (Walsh, 2018, p. 20). Vermaseren suggested that this may have been a *lararium* for household gods (CIMRM 246). One entered the mithraeum by descending a long flight of steps (Fig 25). It had no benches (probably for lack of room) though the suggestion that it was a mithraeum comes from the presence of an altars dedicated to the torchbearers Cautes and Cautopates (CIMRM 358-9) and a marble tauroctony (CIMRM 357).

A.B. Griffith has discussed the mithraeum on the Via St. Giovanni Lanza, suggesting that its layout is overall problematic as it does not conform to expected patterns of mithraea across Italy and the wider empire (Griffith, 2000). There is also considerable debate over the owner of the *Domus*. Vermaseren suggested it belonged to a Flavius Septimius Zozimus due to an inscription relating him to a *spelaeum* nearby (CIL 6.733).

Figure 25 Section drawing of the entrance to the mithraeum (CIMRM 246-60)

Again, in Ostia the presence of mithraea in private housing complexes are even more evident. At the *insulae* apartment known as the 'House of Diana, a series of two rooms were found which were originally living spaces and then later turned into a mithraeum (Fig 26). The construction of the house itself probably dates to the early 2nd century and then later modified to resemble a Mithraic sanctuary at the beginning of the 3rd century (CIMRM 216). According to Vermaseren, the floors had originally been covered in mosaic and the room was separated by a partition wall, on the right side of which was an interior window (ibid).

In terms of the cult images that were present, the tauroctony is believed to have been lost, though a main altar survives which has a pierced circular hole through its middle. Vermaseren suggested that it may have been moved from another location (ibid). Moreover, the altar was clearly presented upside-down and reused for the purposes of this mithraeum. Its previous use is attested to a faint inscription dedicated to the Greek god Hercules, which might otherwise indicate that the community here either did not have enough money or resources to commission their own altar, or perhaps what we see here is some form of religious syncretism (ibid). In any case, what we can clearly suggest is that the community was mobile, and this is further supported by epigraphic evidence of the altar's dedicator M. Lollianus Callinicus. He refers to himself as *pater* suggesting he was the leader of this particular Mithraic community, though his name also appears to be connected to an earlier religious structure nearby, which may well have served the purpose of a mithraeum (ibid). On the base of this altar, there is also a small head to the Greek deity Dionysus (CIMRM 218).

Figure 26 Mithraeum at the House of Diana, Ostia. C: Altar, B: Central nave, A: Narthex, a: Basin (CIMRM 216)

Gaul

Unlike in Italy, all known mithraea in Gaul are stand-alone structures and their distribution is very much concentrated in the western half of the province (Walsh, 2018, p. 17). In terms of their layouts and structural features, all seem to incorporate very standard traits in what can only be considered most basic. They all fit the layout according to Beck; that is, they are underground to some degree, have opposing benches and an apsal feature. Despite this, it would seem that a number of gallic mithraea follow a trend in which they are closely associated with both natural and artificial water features (ibid, pp. 18-19) (Fig 27). The artificial features usually present themselves as hypocausts, drains/gullies, basins or fountains and the natural features form part of mithraeum's immediate landscape, as either rivers or springs (ibid).

Figure 27 Map by Walters (1974, index)

In some cases, mithraea are very closely situated near known bath-houses, as is the case at both Les Bolards (CIMRM 917) and Vieux-en-Val Romey (CIMRM 909-914). The latter site lies north of the Rhône Valley and excavations undertaken in the 19th century revealed an unusually large structure, inside which was a water channel running in its western corner (Desjardins, 1870, p. 13). Dating of the site comes from numismatic evidence. Coins of Claudius Gothicus give an estimated date of use between 296-70 CE, though Harold Mattingly is credited for suggesting that some of these may well have been later forgeries (Mattingly, 1928, pp. 202-3). In any case, further excavation of the area revealed that the mithraeum was surrounded by what in appearance resembled a bath house complex. Walters suggested that the site at Vieu is very similar to the sanctuary of Apollo-Moritasgus in Alise-Saint-Reine (Walters, 1974, pp. 10-11), in which the temple is enclosed by an area with several bath-houses devoted to healing (Toutain, 1932, pp. 193-4).

At Les Bolards (CIMRM 917) near Nuites-Saint-Georges a fairly large mithraeum was uncovered to the north of an even larger temple and possible vicus spanning 12 hectares (Thévenot, 1948) (Fig 28). It contained opposing benches and was entered via three steps at a depth of 1.3m below the Roman surface. To the north of the mithraeum was a very large hypocaust which likely ran into the nearby spring of La Courtavaux (Thévenot, 1948 pp. 302-4).

As Walsh has pointed out, various other mithraea exhibit smaller associations with water, though the presence of water features is undoubted. At Septeuil near Paris, is a mithraeum that manipulated a former *nymphaeum* into the site, which in turn was enclosed by a spring (Walsh, 2018, p. 18). It was similarly surrounded by a larger complex which could otherwise be a bath-house (ibid). Similarly, preliminary excavations undertaken by Jean-Jacques Hatt in 1955 uncovered a mithraeum in the Bas-Rhin region of northern France. It was also likely surrounded by a bath-house, though more curious are the remains of a wooden temple dedicated to an unknown deity (Hatt, 1955, p. 409).

Figure 28 Plan of Les Bolards, Mithraeum to the north of the central temple and vicus (Pommeret, 2001, p. 24)

In returning to the evidence from Les Bolards, another significant discovery was made in the large hypocaust to the north. Inside the hypocaust were various anatomical *ex votos*, religious offerings which took the shape of a specific body part. In their most general definition, anatomical *ex votos* were gifted to a deity in thanks for curing a specific ailment. It was almost always the problematic body part which was resembled on a particular material and then gifted (Draycott & Graham, 2017, pp. 1-19). In Italy, *ex votos* were sometimes highly visible, though many were simply placed in necropoli, sanctuaries or temples specifically dedicated to healing (Venters, 2019, p. 11). However, it would seem that in Gaul this act of ritual offering was undertaken by throwing such votives into water sources. At Bolards, they were crafted out of bronze and made to resemble human eyes (Walters 1974, p. 14). Similarly, a number of *ex votos* crafted into legs were found within the mithraeum itself (ibid).

Walter comments that at Vieu-en-Val-Romey, similar eye offerings were discovered in the sanctuary's northern water channel, alongside remnants of ash and animal bones (p. 8). The comparison she makes with the shrine of Apollo-Moritasgus at Alise St. Reine is very well supported as here also were *ex votos* that mirrored those found at Vieu (Fig 29). The shrine at Alise-Saint-Reine was not only surrounded by a bath house complex, but also buildings dedicated to various healing deities. This coupled with the discovery of surgical equipment would indicate that doctors were also here (Walters, 1974 p. 10). The connection between the two sites is further exemplified in the discovery of a head to the deity of Apollo north of mithraeum at Vieu (CIMRM 913).

Figure 29 Anatomical ex votos of eyes, from the shrine of Apollo-Moritasgus, Alise St. Reine. Similar in description to those found at Les Bolards and Vieu (de Cazanove, et al. 2012, p. 114)

Britain

At Rudchester mithraeum, the sanctuary was intentionally constructed close to a nearby stream and a water basin, fairly contemporary with the period, was found nearby (CIMRM 838). Inside the basin were various iron implements, one of which Vermaseren described as a candlestick (*ibid*). At Housesteads, near Hadrian's wall a similar basin was uncovered close to a spring (CIMRM 852). It was constructed of brick and had excess gutters in which water could have been drained. George Boon, responsible for the 1959 excavations of the Roman fort at Caernarvon is credited for discovering the only known mithraeum in Wales (Boon, 1960). He found the remains of a drain inside the mithraeum, which carried water to a nearby stream. He compared this directly with Housesteads, in which a spring-fed cistern was also found (pp. 136-78).

With the exception of the items found in the basin at Rudchester, the majority of these mithraea do not provide any other forms of evidence in which we can confidently say that water rituals were part of cult activity. However, if we turn to the mithraea at Carrawburgh and London, the archaeology seems to paint a more concrete picture of this. At Carrawburgh, located west of milecastle 31 on Hadrian's wall, a well was found with an altar dedicated to the local nymphs and Genius Loci (Mayers, 2017, p. 19). Though it seemed to have fallen into disuse fairly early, its presence likely indicates a connection to healing deities (Smith, 1962). This could be further supported in the existence of 'Coventina's well', a nearby shrine which was the centre of worship for a traditional Celtic water goddess (Allason-Jones & McKay, 1985). At the Walbrook mithraeum in London, as well as being very closely situated near the Walbrook stream, the temple had a timber-lined well incorporated into its southern aisle (Fig 30). According to John Shepherd, the well was likely in use between 240-50 CE and used for ritual purposes (Shepherd, 1998, p. 71) (Fig 30).

Figure 30 *Timber-lined well from the Walbrook mithraeum, London.*
(Shepherd, 1998, p. 73)

The mithraea in Britain also provide a great deal of evidence for food consumption. Anthony King's 2005 study on the prevalence of faunal remains at Romano-British temples has proved very informative about patterns of consumption and the possibility for distinct feasting practices among British mithraea (King, 2005, pp. 353-355). At Carrawburgh, King took note of the areas in which different bones were recovered and attempted to pattern them with known phases of occupation at the mithraeum (Fig 31). Various bones were noted in the narthex, nave and even within the revetments of the opposing benches. In its earliest phases (mid 3rd century), it would seem that ox, sheep and pig bones were deposited on the floor of the narthex; King also notes that all of the bones belonged to fairly younger animals (p. 354). The next phase of occupation was characterised by the covering of nave's floor with heather flower and scattered

throughout were the leg and wing bones of ‘many’ chickens. In the original excavation report, this is suggested as representing some form of votive offering after a ritual meal (Richmond & Gillam, 1951, pp. 16-18). In the following century, King comments on the discovery of a ceramic vessel, in which were the charred remains of pinecones and the head and neck of a chicken (p. 355). It was apparently carefully placed in the foundation rubble near the apse of the structure and might represent some form of closing ritual (Richmond & Gillam, 1951, pp. 35-6). This does coincide with the 4th century demolition of the mithraeum, a period in which ox and sheep bones were dumped in the building’s rubble (King, 2005, p. 355)

	Ox	Sheep /Goat	Pig	Chicken	Goose
Narthex, Phase IIA	2	7	13	-	-
‘Ordeal-pit’, Phase IIB	-	2	-	-	-
Nave, Phase IIC	-	3	5	-	-
Ante-room, Phase IIC	-	2	6	-	-
Bench revetments, Phases II and III	-	-	3	‘many’	8
Nave, Phase III	1	3	5	-	-
Deposit beneath altars, Phase III	-	-	-	cranium	-

Figure 31 Animal remains from Carrawburgh (Fraser, 1951). **Phase I:** Early 3rd century, **Phase II:** Mid 3rd century, **Phase III:** Mid to late 4th century

Total bones from in and near the mithraeum			
Ox	98	Chicken	192
Sheep/Goat	28	Duck (dom.)	4
Pig	58	Duck sp.	2
		Goose sp.	1
		Scolopax rusticola	1
		Corvus corax	1

Figure 32 The Walbrook mithraeum, London (Macready & Sidell, 1998, table 33)

Similarly, at London's Walbrook mithraeum, King notes that the most prevalent animal remains in its earliest phase (c.240-50 CE) were chicken bones (p. 353-4) (Fig 32). It would seem that some of these bones were intentionally deposited in the walls and floors of the structure (Macready & Sidell, 1998, pp. 210-14). However, as is the case Carrawburgh, fourth century phases are absent of chicken altogether, with an increased number of sheep and ox (King, 2005, p. 354). John Shepherd has also commented on the evidence for intense burning on the mithraeum's floors, something which he suggests could be indicative of food preparation within the temple (Shepherd, 1998, p. 74).

The Walbrook mithraeum, is by far Britain's largest. It has a length of over 60ft and a width of about 25ft (CIMRM 814) (Fig 33). Fortunately, its close vicinity with the Walbrook stream has created some of the best water-logged conditions in Roman London and consequently, much of its original material has been well preserved. Alongside the deposited animal bones of the 4th century, excavators uncovered marble busts of various cult statues. One belonged to Mithras, one Serapis, Minerva and another to a possible Oceanus (Fig 34) (CIMRM 810-26)

Other non-Mithraic statues were uncovered alongside the bust of Serapis (Fig 35) and a relief of Bacchus from the same period was found buried in the floor of the nave (CIMRM 822) (Fig 36). Vermaseren is credited for suggesting that the presence of primarily non-Mithraic iconography during this period indicates that the mithraeum may well have been rededicated to another deity (CIMRM 822). In fact, the marble relief of Bacchus is inscribed with the words '*Hominibus Bagis Bitam*' meaning 'giver of life to wondering men' (RIB 1). Valerie Hutchinson has suggested that this particular phrase references the cult of Bacchus' beliefs of the afterlife, in which the Greek deity Dionysus grants joy and pleasure through wine and sex (Hutchinson, 1986, p. 136).

Figure 33 Plan of the Walbrook mithraeum, London (Merrifield, 1983, p. 184)

Figure 34 *Bust of Oceanus (CIMRM 813)*

Figure 35 *Head of Serapis, CIMRM 818*

Figure 36 *Relief of Bacchus/Dionysus and Satyrs (CIMRM 822-3)*

Part III

Discussion

In considering the evidence then, it is best to examine and discuss what it tells us in line with the focus of this dissertation: localisation. The primary aim of this work was to give a preliminary overview of some of the most significant pieces of evidence we have for the development of localisation in Mithraism. With that said, it is equally important that we try to posit the potential reasons for the occurrence of such variation in the first place, rather than simply trying to piece together its historical narratives. In fact, it is worth considering what the evidence might tell us about the individuals who worshipped Mithras, their sense of identity and, of course, their experiences in an increasingly dynamic world. Understanding the mechanisms of change and development in Mithraism is an undoubtedly difficult task to achieve, however, it is hoped that this discussion will cultivate ideas that are not only useful in the study of Mithraism, but stimulating, so as to showcase the inherent problems within our current modes of understanding.

First, it would be useful identifying the regional trends that are apparent in the evidence for Mithraism. If we are to accept that the Cult first developed in Italy, then it is viable to suggest that the evidence belongs to a somewhat 'proto-Mithraism,' in which many of its features and characteristics have set the precedent for the development of homogeneity elsewhere. This is not simply speculation. The earliest forms of Mithraic iconography do indeed derive from the city of Rome (Fig 17), at a time when it is nowhere else to be seen in the western empire. If therefore, our current models are to be accepted, then it would seem only natural for scholars to support this interpretation.

In terms of the wider picture of Mithraic iconography in Italy, what can be said is that all conform to the underlying and basic visual characteristics that are expected within our current visual understanding of the cult. That is to say, that all of the tauroctony scenes are simply that, Mithras killing the bull. He is always surrounded by his Companions Cautes and Cautopates and he is also always wearing Persian dress. However, one particularly distinct aspect to some of the depictions of this scene in Italy, is that some are painted as frescos instead of sculpted in marble. Of course, the vast majority are indeed sculpted in relief, though if anything, this would suggest to us that there existed a certain degree of deviation among cult communities in Italy. The presence of such deviation does not necessarily present a picture in which

communities were distinctly different and nor does it suggest anything remotely different about the narrative of Mithras killing the bull. However, it does support that religious expression and thus experience of the tauroctony was varied for some followers of the cult. Of course, the reason as to why some communities decided to paint their tauroctony scenes, rather than commission them in sculpture, might be as simple as for pragmatism or access to resources. Though, one suspects this to be a fairly unsatisfactory interpretation. In fact, it might be worth trying to understand what the use of paint instead of stone or marble for iconography tells us about the individuals who were responsible for commissioning them in the first place.

Elizabeth Pye's publication on the colour, design and technology of Roman wall paintings in Italy discusses the types of material that were part of paint pigments (Pye, 2000). She indicates that although many colours used were derived from pigments taken from naturally occurring compounds, some, such as Egyptian blue and red were evidently rarer (p. 24). In fact, though Egyptian blue was very popular in Rome, the actual process of obtaining the mineral compound for it (cuprorivaite) was difficult and expensive (McCouat, 2018, p. 1). In considering that many painted frescoes of Mithras utilise both rare pigments of blue and red, we can discern that the resources and money needed for the commissioning of such pieces, were thus significantly large. Of course, in the city of Rome, there is only one known mithraeum with a painted tauroctony, the Barberini (CIMRM 390) (Fig 17). As discussed previously, it was actually more common for mithraea in Ostia to incorporate painting reliefs, than in Rome. Moreover, some Ostian mithraea incorporated mosaics, such as at the 'Planta Pedis (CIMRM 272) and Sette Sfere (CIMRM 239), which would have otherwise been expensive to commission and therefore indicative of high-status followers.

In thinking about this, it might worth trying to understand what types of people followers of the cult of Mithras in Italy were. Evidently, the elaboration and decoration of iconography in Italian mithraea suggests that the individuals involved in the worship of Mithras belonged to higher stratas of Roman society. This is perhaps more apparent in the various dedication inscriptions found within them. An inscription from the Mithraeum at St. Clemente, Rome was dedicated by one Gnaeus Arius Claudianus (CIMRM 340), who is clearly a member of the elite patrician *gens Claudia*. Similarly,

Vermaseren's suggestion that the mithraeum at Via St. Giovanni Lanza belonged to one Flavius Septimius Zozimus, which if true would suggest he was owner of its associated *Domus*, a type of house which was predominantly owned by elite Romans (Métraux, 1999). Even the earliest tauroctony relief we have for the cult in Italy (CIMRM 593-4) was dedicated by a slave of Tiberius Claudius Livianus, one of Rome's praetorian prefects (Clauss, 2000, p. 22). Though this might suggest that the cult was initially favoured among military elite in the city, they belonged to an elite class, nonetheless.

Moving away from the iconography, a somewhat universal trend among Italian mithraea besides excellent decoration and elaboration, would be the construction of them within or in addition to pre-existing structures. This is not just the case in Rome, but also in Ostia. Some were evidently later additions to public buildings as is the case at the Crypta Balbi (Figs 23-4) and the Circus Maximus (CIMRM 434). Others formed parts of houses, both elite and non-elite, as is the case with Giovanni Lanza in Rome and the House of Diana in Ostia (Fig 26). In terms of what we can gauge about this particular development, is that the fact it occurs across a number of different types of buildings, suggests the reason for doing so may have been more pragmatic, than religious.

This is a viable interpretation if we consider that at the turn of the 2nd century, the population of Rome was in excess of one million inhabitants (Oates, 1934). The erection of *insulae* apartments across the city alongside major infrastructural developments would have meant that there simply was not enough room for mithraists to construct stand-alone sanctuaries, particularly considering the increasingly obvious expectation that they were to be constructed underground or in representation of a cave. They may have simply had to make do with the space they had within in an urban environment. One might put to question the reasons as to why mithraea in Ostia were also similarly constructed and the answer would be that Ostia's growth as a centre for maritime trade meant that the town developed in many ways as Rome did, fast paced and distinctly urban. Consequently, the decision to construct mithraea in the same way here was equally as pragmatic.

Moving onto the ritual trends that we can discern from Italy; little can actually be said due to the generally ephemeral nature of ritualistic activity. What we expect to see is

evidence of feasting, through animal bones or ceramics. However, it would seem that much of the archaeological evidence is either unidentified or absent altogether. This does not necessarily mean that Mithraic communities in Italy did not engage in the likes of ritual feasting, but rather perhaps the process of ritual activity was different than what we see elsewhere in the empire, leaving behind a less distinctive archaeological signature.

With that said, Vermaseren's overview of the initiation scenes from Capua Vetere (CIMRM 187-193) has proved useful in conceptualising the outward appearance of ritual activity in the cult. As stated earlier, though we may not be able to completely trust the Christian sources about the nature of Mithraic initiations, they cannot be completely disregarded. In fact, many of them were writing in Italy during the 2nd century, as is the case with Tertullian. In this instance, the archaeological and iconographic evidence for ritual activity can be appropriately accompanied with the literary evidence and therefore the panels at Capua Vetere might be our only chance at visually conceptualising what exactly an initiation in the cult of Mithras entailed. However, with the lack of visual stimuli outside of Italy, we may never truly understand the extent to which initiation practices were varied across the empire.

What does seem to be happening in Italy, however, is a degree of religious syncretism within the cult. At the House of Diana, a head of the Greek god Dionysus/Bacchus was carved into the altar (CIMRM 216), the very same altar that was once dedicated to the deity Hercules before it was turned upside down and used in the mithraeum (ibid). Similarly, at Capua Vetere the relief dedicated to Eros/Amor and Psyche (CIMRM 186) is not only unexpected, but it is the first instance we see them associated with Mithras in the entire Empire (Luther M, 2015 p. 107). One possible reason for the association between the two has been discussed by Martin Luther. He suggests that the scene is usually present in the Eleatic traditions of Magna Graecia and that Amor is commonly represented leading Psyche by torchlight (Luther, M, 2015, p. 110). It is the torchlight that is symbolically representative of salvation from darkness into light, a concept which is understood to have accompanied Mithraic initiations (ibid). Luther goes on to say that the incorporation of the relief into a Mithraic context was quite simply an ordinary process of human cognition, in that the scene was not only recognizable but fundamentally part of classical myth and therefore it was ordinary to associate the symbolic traits of Mithras with those of

Amor and Psyche (p. 112). If a viable interpretation, then the cult of Mithras in Italy was permeable and allowed for the inclusion of traditional Graeco-Roman deities. However, the extent to which these deities were 'worshipped' in the same sense as Mithras, seems to be questionable. Instead, such practices were accompanied with an understanding of personified mythical themes which were relevant to the inherent ideologies in Mithraism and therefore, the incorporation of mythical iconography was natural and purely symbolic.

In Gaul, a different story can be told regarding the development of Mithraism. This is particularly the case with mithraea, which were otherwise stand-alone structures and not connected to pre-existing buildings (Walsh, 2018, p. 17). This would seem to be a province-wide trend, with the exception of those that are in the immediate vicinity of bath-house complexes (ibid). In thinking about the reasons for this, unlike in Rome and wider Italy, many of the mithraea in Gaul were not concentrated in large urban centres and therefore their use of space was not as limited. Consequently, founders of Mithraic communities were able to consider where was best to build their sanctuaries. Of course, some are indeed closely associated with urban spaces, such as at Les Bolards (CIMRM 917), though even in this instance the structure is located outside of the confines of the possible *vicus* (Thévenot, 1948).

Even more apparent at Gallic mithraea is that the vast majority of them were built near natural or artificial water sources (Walsh, 2018, p. 17-18). In Italy, this does not seem to be the case at all, with the exception of the 'Baths of Mithras' in Ostia (CIMRM 229). In considering the possible reasons as to why it was necessary for mithraea here to be located near water sources, we can probably rule out any practical use. The fact that many structures were constructed partly underground would have created conditions in which many were susceptible to flooding and major water damage. We know that this was a frequent problem for the Walbrook in London (Myers, 2016, p. 1) and also at Carrawburgh near Hadrian's Wall (Drummond, 2013, p. 29). As a result, we can probably assume that the intention behind the locating of mithraea near water sources, was probably connected to some widely established Mithraic custom, that may well have been universally practiced across communities in Gaul and perhaps Britain. Of course, understanding what this entailed is naturally difficult for lack of objective evidence. However, the use of water in ancient religions is not unheard of and in particular its significance in Roman healing cults is widely understood (Edlund-

Berry, 2006). This latter point is especially relatable in regards to the votive evidence from Gaul. It might be viable to suggest that the presence of anatomical *ex votos* at both Les Bolards and Vieu supports that some of the Mithraic rituals that took place at these sites were concerned with healing. This is even more apparent in considering the close associations that can be made between these two sites and temple of Apollo-Moritasgus at Alise St. Reine, in which various surgical equipment was uncovered (Walters, 1974 p. 10).

If we are to assume that common water rituals took place at mithraea in Gaul, then we might try and consider the reasons for such a development in the first place. One potential cause might be found in the province's pre-Roman roots and the ritual activity that was practiced among Celtic people before the advent of Roman paganism. During Bronze and Iron Age Europe, a number of communities considered rivers, streams and other natural water sources as highly venerable places (Pintar, 2016, pp. 7-9). One significant religious practice that took place was the intentional deposition of various objects, especially metals, into these natural sources (Wells, 1990, p. 462).

In Gaul, the act of depositing *ex votos* in water might therefore be considered a product of continued religious practice, one that was well established centuries, if not millennia before the arrival of the Romans. If viable, there are a few significant deductions we can make about the nature of religion in Roman Gaul. First, if water deposition is indeed a continued religious practice, we can probably make the assumption that indigenous people in Gaul were very much aware of their Celtic roots. In support of this, the Roman name for the settlement at Vieu-en-Val-Romey was '*Venetonimagus*' (Walters, 1974, p. 5-11). This particular name seems to be an amalgamation of Latin and Celtic origins, the end *-Magus* likely being the Celtic term for 'forum' (Grenier, 1934, p. 695). Secondly, it undoubtedly supports the idea that the Romans did not set out to destroy Celtic culture. If anything, rituals involving anatomical *ex votos* were inherently Roman, though when coupled with their deposition into water, we can see a fusion of two very distinct religious practices.

In terms of what this might tell us about the nature of Mithraism, the evidence here supports that the cult was highly susceptible to religious syncretism, even in Gaul. The fact we see similar syncretic associations with non-Mithraic deities in the iconography from Italy not only maintains this assimilative nature of the cult, but also supports that

localisation took precedence in the development of religious expression. That is to say that what was happening in Italy was not necessarily happening in Gaul and that communities from both provinces developed their own qualities due to the intrinsic permeable and assimilative nature of Roman, Greek and Celtic paganism.

What about the types of people who were followers of Mithras in Gaul? Unlike in Italy, understanding this is evidently more complicated. We cannot make basic assumptions based on the architectural traits or locations of mithraea here. In response, Walters has commented on some of the epigraphic material, particularly the *cognomen* of dedicants to various mithraea in the province. She has suggested that a large number of people who dedicated altars to mithraea across Gaul have predominantly Greek names (Walters, 1974, p. 31). It would seem that this is especially the case in areas near the mouth of the Rhône valley, where the mithraeum at Vieu was located (ibid). She goes on to suggest that it is likely that Mithraism spread into Gaul via this area and the presence of an inscription from Vieu in which the Mithraic *pater* shares a Greek *cognomen* supports that it may well have been one of the first Mithraic communities in the province (p. 32).

A possible interpretation of this, could be that original followers of the cult were of non-local origin and either from Italy or Magna Graecia. However, at Les Bolards, epigraphic evidence is characterised by an increased number of indigenous Gallic people (p. 33). Interpretations put forward by J.J Hatt propose that many mithraists here were likely local people who had abandoned the countryside for the security of the local *vicus* (Hatt, 1951, p. 27). He also goes on to say that the area was incredibly important for the recruitment of Roman soldiers and that the establishment of the mithraeum may well have been associated with the large military presence (ibid).

In any case, it would seem that the cult was brought to Gaul by men with Greek names. locations of mithraea near important military and trade routes suggest that the people who were involved in the worship of Mithras had fairly diverse backgrounds. With that said, one cannot disregard the role of the military altogether, as we know that the cult was extremely popular with Roman soldiers across the empire (Campbell, 2013). Consequently, we might infer that, more so than in Italy, people who considered themselves to be followers of Mithras came from many different backgrounds, some

militarist, some local and others from more 'exotic' provinces. In this sense, the cult of Mithras was more accessible to a wider range of people, than in Italy.

Finally, in turning our attention to Britain, the evidence here might initially seem to imitate what we have in Gaul. This is somewhat understandable considering that mithraea here follow the same layouts and incorporate similar architectural features. This is also further supported by the fact that Mithraic communities likely used water for various rituals in Britain, as is commonly demonstrated in Gaul. In fact, it may even be viable to suggest that the use of water in Britain is also representative of continuing pre-Roman rituals, as it is widely known that deposition of metals in water also occurred in Britain during Prehistory (Hingley, 2006, pp. 234-5). This is clearly the case at Coventina's Well near Carrawburgh mithraeum which was used as a shrine to a Celtic healing deity (Allason-Jones & McKay, 1985). From the outset, we would not be mistaken for thinking that the similarities in the archaeology from Britain and Gaul are indicative of a shared religious practice. However, as has been illustrated, suggesting such an idea is in disregard of the many idiosyncrasies that do present themselves in the evidence.

The wealth of animal remains at mithraea in Britain shows that ritual feasting did form part of religious activity here. It would seem that during the 3rd century there was indeed a preference for chicken as opposed to ox and sheep, which occurs more frequently in the following century (King, 2005 p. 353-55). The reasons for this are difficult to discern and there is no evidence to suggest that these animals were sacrificed before being eaten (ibid). However, the scattering of animal bones, as opposed to accidental refuse is a point of interest, which alongside the intentional scattering of heather flower at Carrawburgh supports that the process of feasting was accompanied with some form of ritual activity.

The most promising form of evidence we have for localisation in Britain, however, is the depositional objects that were uncovered at London's Walbrook (CIMRM 814). As already discussed, intentional deposition is common in mithraea across the empire and the practice is by no means isolated to animal bones. As discussed in Part I, many mithraea deposited a number of different things, some of which were fragmented ceramics with Mithraic iconography on them (Fig 15), some perhaps foundation boxes,

as is the case in Roman Dacia, at Apulum III (McCarty, 2019). Others are less conspicuous, such as the deposition of items into water features in Gaul. In Britain, one would assume that its close resemblance to Mithraism in Gaul might suggest some shared depositional practices also, however, it would seem that the Mithraic community in London practiced something completely different to what we have come across so far. Towards the end of the mithraeum's use, the followers here took it upon themselves to bury a number of non-Mithraic statues within the sanctuary (CIMRM 810-26). The marble busts discussed in part II all belonged to the first half of the 4th century (Shepherd, 1998, pp. 161-174), and included heads of Mithras (CIMRM 815), the Egyptian Serapis (CIMRM 818), Minerva (CIMRM 820) and the water deity Oceanus (CIMRM 813) alongside a relief of a reclining Mercury (CIMRM 821). The heads were clearly intentionally decapitated due to the clean nature of the cuts, and it is assumed they would have been kept within the mithraeum for votive purposes (Shepherd, 1998 pp. 161-174).

Besides being evidence for a distinct depositional ritual, the most fascinating observation is that there is more non-Mithraic iconography here than Mithraic, despite the fact that the structure was evidently used for the purpose of worshipping Mithras. The presence of other deities is not as simple as what we can infer from Italy due to the possibility that they would have been worshipped alongside Mithras. Their purpose within the mithraeum cannot therefore be considered symbolically representative of classical themes, as is the case with the Amor and Psyche relief from Capua Vetere (CIMRM 186). Instead, we might bring ourselves back to the idea that the cult of Mithras was fundamentally assimilative and therefore highly susceptible to influence from other established pantheons. It might suggest to us that the mithraists here used other deities as a platform to further emulate the divine properties of their Mithras, who was otherwise the most central character to the cult's religious narratives.

Again, thinking about the types of people who were followers of the cult in Britain, it is even more clear that the god was favoured among military men. To date, mithraea have been found at Carrawburgh (CIMRM 844), Housesteads (CIMRM 852), Rudchester (CIMRM 838) and Caernarvon (CIMRM 2374), all of which are associated with various Roman legionary forts or Hadrian's Wall, as is the case with the first two.

The only exception could be the Walbrook, although an inscription was dedicated by one Ulpian Silvanus, a veteran of the Second Augustan Legion (RIB 3) (Harris & Harris, 1965, p. 7). It is also worth remembering that the presence of the Roman Army is well established in London by the 2nd century CE (De la Bédoyère, 2002, p. 177) and consequently, it would not be plausible to consider this community as being any less appealing to soldiers (or ex-soldiers) than anywhere else in the province.

One might ponder the extent to which followers of the Mithras could recognize the cult in various contexts. Say, for example, a mithraist, who had been born in the city of Rome at the turn of the 3rd century, packed up and moved to Britain. In joining a new fraternity, would he still be able to recognize the cult as he knew it? Could he share with his new-founded brothers his well-established cosmological knowledge, without running the risk of being ousted as a madman? How would he have known there existed a cult dedicated to Mithras in the first place? These are the questions which scholars ought to be asking if we are to further our understanding of Roman Mithraism.

Conclusion

With all things considered, it is hoped that this dissertation has provided an account of Mithraism that is not only diverse, but useful in conceptualising the extent to which variation can manifest in the development of Roman religion. The cult and all of its associated characteristics were subject to its local and regional contexts; it is through this process of localisation that Mithraism developed both small and large scale transformations. The notion that homogeneity supports shared experience is in complete disregard of circumstantial influence. It forgets to consider the lived experience of individuals, their cognitive processes and conceptions of a self and community identity. Of course, a number of scholars today are becoming increasingly aware of the inherent problems within our frameworks but little has been done to present or interpret the evidence for localisation within Mithraism. Perhaps even to use the word 'Mithraism' is to make an interpretive leap about aspects of the cult, which otherwise plainly refute the concept that it belonged to a universally standardised religious institution.

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